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A Review of National Elementary School Curricula in relation to Experiential Education, Game-Based Learning and Education for Sustainable Development

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Abstract: The differences between education systems have been a prevalent topic to study in educational research. Similarly, increased knowledge of pedagogical approaches and schools as organizations has helped develop teaching-learning processes on various levels. National curricula are constantly updated and remain an intriguing research topic due to their ability to characterize how education and its practices are viewed and organized. This study aims to describe the curricula in three European countries, namely Austria, Finland and Hungary. Specifically, the comparison focuses on the visibility of contemporary educational approaches (i.e., experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning and education for sustainable development). The results show that the approaches have been incorporated into the curricula in different ways, varying from a shared value underlying the entire curriculum to specific practices on the lesson or content level. Going forward, there is a need for considering the dimensionality and comprehensiveness of these approaches to better understand their foundational characteristics.

Introduction

Curriculum planning is an essential aspect of education, changing the ways in which teaching and learning are organized across different subjects (see e.g. Voogt & Roblin, 2012; Ahmad et al., 2023). In general, providing comprehensive descriptions of educational processes can be viewed as a way to promote the interconnectedness and consistency of teaching and learning both within and between educational institutions, also addressing potential barriers (e.g., related to geographic location). However, curricula can also become rigid or disconnected from teachers'

and students' everyday life, emphasizing the importance of flexibility and the creation of meaningful requirements that correspond to daily teaching activities (see e.g., Jonker et al., 2020).

Although the contents and the role of curriculum depends on the country in question, there are similarities in the pedagogical practices that are generally followed in curriculum planning. For example, equipping students with 21st-century skills is viewed as an important task for many educational institutions (Chalkiadaki, 2018; Dilekçi & Karatay, 2023). Although subject-specific skills and content knowledge continue to be valued, there is an ongoing debate regarding how to match traditional education practices with the more obscure requirements associated with contemporary education (e.g., regarding cross-curricular entities). As curricula and educational practices become increasingly researched and start to entail various cyber-physical layers, it is important to build clarity within this newfound complexity of educational approaches and create strategies for their mindful inclusion into the curriculum planning process.

This research aims to describe the curricula used in three European countries, namely Austria, Finland and Hungary, in order to inspect how contemporary educational approaches are considered in existing guidelines and requirements stemming from diverse pedagogical traditions. More precisely, the study focuses on experiential education, game-based learning and education for sustainable development, all of which are foundational approaches to education that connect learning and teaching processes to students' own lives and the skills they might need in the future. The study attempts to answer the question of *how well European curricula address educational approaches that are relevant to contemporary education (i.e., experiential education, game-based learning, and education for sustainable development)*. The research is carried out as a curriculum comparison and contributes to research by inspecting these educational approaches as interlinked entities and by demonstrating the ways in which they have been incorporated into existing curricula (e.g. in terms of level and comprehensiveness of descriptions). The research also has practical implications for curriculum planning and the teaching of complex topics. The study has been carried out as a part of the Erasmus+ funded STEAMCRAFT project that aims to foster STEM-oriented education in virtual worlds through customized Minecraft modifications.

Background

Curriculum Planning and the Role of National Curricula

Curriculum development can be viewed as a challenging aspect of educational reform due to its complexity and the dynamic environment in which it occurs – although curriculum should support teaching activities, teaching itself is a multifaceted, layered process (Henson, 2015, p. 7). For example, the attitudes, beliefs, competences and practices employed by teachers can determine whether or not changes in teaching and learning practices are realized in the classroom (Voogt & Roblin, 2012). Thus, the effects of curriculum reform on classroom practices are not always straightforward.

Although previous studies show that having national-level control of curricula can include benefits (e.g., coherence and higher test performance), the role of centralization can also be challenged (Schmidt & Prawat, 2006). For example, curriculum-level specifications might not be very detailed and other existing materials, such as past examination papers, can be used by teachers to guide teaching practices (Millar, 2011). Similarly, studies examining the role of a national curriculum show that teachers can interpret policy texts differently – there can be various strategies for interpretation, affected by factors such as teacher's perceptions of how the curriculum is expected to be interpreted, as well as their own experiences (Curtner-Smith, 1999). Thus, the interpretation process itself consists of complex interactions between teachers' subject-specific knowledge and specific knowledge pertaining to their own students (Ross, 2023). This calls for an emphasis on defining a meaningful role for the national curriculum in light of daily educational practices, including a manageable structure (e.g., by using clear language that is approachable to teachers; see Boesen et al., 2014).

Contemporary Approaches to Crafting Engaging Teaching and Learning Experiences

Pedagogical principles can emphasize practical aspects of education (i.e., good practices) but also characterize underlying values on a more general level (Atjonen et al., 2011). This suggests that a national curriculum can constitute a multidimensional entity with varying connections to daily teaching. Although pedagogy is often discussed at the level of content knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge (Kind, 2009), teachers can also employ more generic pedagogical principles in their teaching. For example, teachers' experiences of successful educational events can relate to their relationship with the pupils and the learning environment, as well as the teaching-

learning arrangements and methods (Atjonen et al., 2011). Thus, the external expectations and practical choices made by teachers create a complex playing field for the educational practice.

Experiential Education

It is characteristic for contemporary educational approaches to consider the teaching-learning processes on a phenomenological basis, concentrating on learning to learn and placing less emphasis on content-specific knowledge. For example, problem-based pedagogical approaches contest the traditional view of acquiring and mastering content knowledge prior to solving a problem by assuming that knowledge can be gained and developed during the problem-solving process itself (Dabbagh & Dass, 2013). In a similar manner, experiential education relies on the notion that knowledge can be gained through intentional experiences and observations that relate to the physical world (see, e.g., Efstratia, 2014). As the learning and decision-making processes in the modern society are becoming increasingly complex, there is a need to facilitate these kinds of individual learning experiences in order to address multifaceted contemporary issues such as climate change (Higgins, 2009).

Although cross-cutting approaches to education have immense value, content-specific pedagogies sustain their relevance as well. For example, there has been an increase in studies focusing on innovative teaching strategies used in chemistry education, including approaches such as inquiry-based learning, virtual and device-based learning and context-based learning (Ahmad et al., 2023). In fact, pedagogical innovation is an integral part of creating new ways of working for schools. Shared learning environments between interlinked subjects, together with common practices and new tools, can support innovative learning activities among both teachers and students (Jaatinen & Lindfors, 2019). Thus, it is essential for educational institutions to find a balance between traditional and innovative approaches to education.

Game-Based Learning

While play is not a new phenomenon in the field of education, the emergence of digital games has evoked interest towards game-based learning and gamification (Plass et al., 2015). For example, both can be viewed as strategies to develop students' foundational (meta-)learning skills and subject-specific knowledge, attaching positive traits to the learning process itself (e.g., through increased motivation and enjoyment; Fernando & Premadasa, 2024). Although the empirical support towards games as effective learning environments varies, the advantages most often associated with these approaches include learner motivation, player engagement, adaptivity to various situations and failure as an in-built and expected feature (Plass et al., 2015). Moreover, digital games can be developed to support complex learning goals in specific subjects such as mathematics (see, e.g., Brezovsky et al., 2019).

Game-based learning can also be viewed as an interplay between learning design, the theories and strategies underlying the curriculum and the practical choices made in the classroom itself – Thus, the knowledge possessed by the teachers matters, and the curriculum itself can become a supporting or a restrictive factor in this process (Allsop & Jessel, 2015). Given the general lack of regulation on game-based learning within curricula, teachers need to know how to dose and control the introduction of video games for students, obtaining the benefits without creating a risk for detrimental outcomes (e.g., addiction; see Skoric et al., 2009).

Education for Sustainable Development

While there are various definitions of sustainability ranging from human-centric to nature-centric approaches, sustainability can be viewed as a central aspect of teaching for the future (Taylor et al., 2015, p.1-3). However, young people should be empowered to view themselves as environmental citizens of today, not only as citizens of tomorrow (Hadjichambis & Paraskeva-Hadjichambi, 2020). Environmental education has traditionally been viewed as employing a passive approach that might not result in tangible changes in environmental behavior, calling for more *holistic, value-laden and action-oriented* initiatives (Taylor et al., 2015, p.4). Similarly, the problems with defining sustainability can be challenging for sustainability education, as knowledge related to the topic can become fragmented, and the practices used can vary (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011).

Although an overcrowded curriculum can hinder sustainability practices (Green & Somerville, 2015), there are also ways to overcome these challenges. For example, a study in the primary school context shows that partnerships extending beyond the school environment were an important aspect of integrated sustainability programs, including student-led pedagogical approaches such as creative problem-solving and inquiry (Green & Somerville, 2015). Thus, contemporary approaches to education seem to include similar, interconnected dimensions calling for a more profound understanding of their core characteristics.

Research Design

The current study used curriculum comparison as a research method, with an interpretive approach to analysis (Adamson & Morris, 2014) in order to describe basic education curricula in three European countries (i.e., Austria, Hungary and Finland). The objective was to examine how educational statements, themes and concepts in the national curricula reflect and operationalize experience-oriented pedagogy, game-based learning and/or education for sustainable development. The STEAMCRAFT project focuses on young people in basic education (10-16 years of age), leaving the pre-primary and higher education contexts out of scope. Young people are a particularly interesting age group for this research due to their ability to master many educational activities independently while still being in the process of learning skills for the future, such as becoming sustainably conscious adults.

In the first phase of the study, the curricula were analyzed using a template which included questions about their pedagogical and formal characteristics (e.g., main dimensions). However, the majority of the questions focused on the visibility of the pedagogical approaches and related concepts. The aim of the process was to 1) characterize the curriculum and its position within the education system and 2) describe the dimensions of the curriculum that are specifically related to contemporary educational approaches.

In the second phase, the characteristics of the curricula were compared and contrasted to form a unified view of the topic. This was viewed as an important step in providing a more comprehensive view on a European level while still remaining on a descriptive level. Because the study was carried out as part of the STEAMCRAFT project, the countries were chosen for the analysis based on the expertise and experience of the associated researchers. In this way, researchers who were familiar with the educational system and the curriculum could carry out the analysis for each country, decreasing the chance of essential aspects being lost in translation. In order to maintain the coherence of the data, the comparison was managed by one of the researchers. However, the results were discussed together with the research group. It should be noted that the curricula are not entirely comparable due to the differences between countries and educational systems. Nevertheless, the comparison provides a basis for understanding the potential and limits of curricular planning and the levels on which complex educational approaches can be accounted for. Table 1 presents the structure and basic information about the curricula included in the analysis.

	Curriculum Structure	Current Curriculum
Austria	The Austrian primary school curriculum is divided into ten interconnected sections, which address key issues from educational objectives to teaching methods, interdisciplinary themes and programs.	Primary School Curriculum (BGBl, 2024)
Finland	The basic education curriculum is divided into grades 1-2, 3-6 and 7-9. For each of these, there are descriptions of subjects to be taught (aim, educational objectives, central contents, evaluation criteria) and descriptions of transversal competencies. Education providers create the local curriculum.	The National Core Curriculum for Basic Education 2014 (The Finnish National Agency for Education, 2014)
Hungary	The national core curriculum includes general and detailed curriculum requirements, developmental requirements (competencies, skills) and minimum performance. Framework curricula serve as an intermediate level between the NAT and local curricula.	The National Core Curriculum (Educational Authority, 2020)

Table 1. Basic Information about the Analyzed Curricula

Results and Discussion

The curriculum analysis shows that the countries have specific ways to address contemporary approaches to education. Generally, experiential education, game-based learning and education for sustainable development were visible in the descriptions of teaching-learning processes in three forms: 1) general level (e.g., underlying values of education), 2) cross-curricular level (e.g., transversal competencies) and 3) subject level (e.g., specific content and teaching practices). However, the comprehensiveness of the descriptions could vary at all levels. Table 2 summarizes the main findings in relation to each national curriculum.

	Experiential Education	Game-Based Learning	Education for Sustainable Development
Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Experimentation and learning innovation (general approach) ● Transferable skills (general approach) ● Citizenship education (interdisciplinary topic) ● Inquiry-based learning (general approach) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Experimentation and learning innovation (general approach) ● Digital literacy (interdisciplinary topic) ● Digital education (contemporary theme) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainability as an interdisciplinary topic ● Environmental awareness ● Global citizenship
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Practical skills and agency (underlying transversal learning entities; discussed together with sustainability topics) ● Specific subjects mention practical situations (e.g., social studies, mathematics, biology) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Specific mentions of games (transversal competencies; specific subjects) ● Use of digital games as a general approach to learning environment use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainability as a core value underlying the curriculum ● Participation, involvement and building a sustainable future (transversal competency) ● Mentions of sustainability topics in other transversal competencies and specific subjects
Hungary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Practice-oriented approach to teaching (general approach) ● Emphasis on relevant problems and real-life situations (natural sciences) ● Project-based and research-based teaching methods (natural sciences) ● Active learning (general approach) ● Learning through observations (teaching recommendation) ● Use of experiential and playful learning, use of experiential pedagogies (learning recommendations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing digital competencies (comprehensive goal; interdisciplinary perspective) ● Digital technology-supported education (general approach, learning recommendation) ● Implementation of lessons outside the traditional classroom environment and applying playful methods (teaching recommendations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fostering ecological awareness and environmental consciousness (general approach) ● Mentions of sustainability topics in specific subjects

Table 2. Analysis of National Curricula in relation to Experiential Education, Game-Based Learning and Education for Sustainable Development

Based on the analysis, it can be stated that the chosen educational approaches are somehow accounted for in all of the selected countries. Although experiential education seems to be discussed on various levels of the curricula, many of these mentions can be characterized by relative vagueness, describing the educational practices on a very

general level. In the case of games and gamification, the curricula tend to lack mentions of digital gaming specifically. However, playful teaching methods and ICT use are referred to. Sustainability as a topic appears to relate to specific subjects but can also be viewed as a comprehensive value underlying curricular planning. Additionally, the approaches can be interconnected in the curricula (e.g., experiential and playful learning). Previous research shows that teachers can also make connections between the educational approaches – for example, in defining game-based learning, teachers can emphasize fun learning experiences, learning by doing and using activities as enablers of learning (Avdiu, 2019).

Experiential Education

Within the *Finnish* curriculum, practice-based learning and experiential education appear in a more fragmented fashion. In relation to transversal learning entities, it is stated that the aim is to “strengthen the application of knowledge and skills to practice and to apply agency that lines with a sustainable lifestyle” (p. 23). Thus, this statement itself combines elements from the experiential and sustainability approaches. Similarly, the transversal competency ‘Participation, involvement and building a sustainable future’ aims to “think about and to practice how to conduct practical actions, through which the students can create a positive change” (p.248). The *Austrian* curriculum has a competence-oriented approach, which focuses on giving students skills that are applicable outside of academic contexts and transferable to real-life challenges. Because of this, teaching in Austrian primary schools encourages students to connect between disciplines. This approach is based on the principle of active, inquiry-based learning, in which students explore, solve problems and reflect on their experiences. However, teachers can have mixed stances towards inquiry-based learning. For example, while the benefits of developing students’ skills might be well recognized, the lack of said skills among students could also prevent the realization of the learning benefits (Hofer et al., 2018).

The *Hungarian* curriculum emphasizes experience-oriented pedagogy through project-based methods and real-life applications, particularly in natural sciences. In the teaching and learning of natural science, it is essential for students to engage with relevant problems and real-life situations. This is achieved through an integrated approach to the presented problems, active student participation, and the planning, execution, observation, and analysis of simple experiments. For example, the curriculum can be viewed to support active, phenomenon-based learning in the field of physics education (Egri et al., 2021). It is believed that an experiential, practice-oriented approach to teaching becomes more successful than traditional, conventional curriculum organization. Historically, the process of developing a national core curriculum for Hungary has included various phases, including debates regarding the balance between state control and the autonomy of schools and teachers (Báthory, 1993).

Game-Based Learning

Although games and gamification are referred to on different occasions throughout the *Finnish* curriculum, the mentions seem to relate to the more foundational nature of play, as well as specific teaching cases. For example, it has been mentioned that “in choosing the ways of working, the possibilities provided by games and gamification are utilized” (p.21). Playing and games are often discussed in parallel, including notions of imagination and narrativeness. For grades 3-9, games are mentioned in relation to the transversal competency of taking care of oneself and managing daily life. In relation to specific subjects, there are notions that gamification and games are important for increasing the motivation of students.

Although the *Austrian* curriculum does not include specific mentions of game-based learning, there are mentions of contemporary themes (e.g., digital education), which are viewed as important entities that are expected to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century (e.g., technological advances and global interdependence). The *Austrian* curriculum also mentions digital literacy as one of the interdisciplinary skills. Because the *Austrian* curriculum refers to experimentation and learning innovation, issues related to game-based learning can also be experimented with. For example, past research has noted that an online game designed for secondary school can help students gain geographical knowledge through an enjoyable learning experience (Ebner et al., 2011). Similar to Austria, the official guidelines for the model curricula in the *Hungarian* system do not explicitly refer to gamification or game-based learning in conjunction with specific subjects. However, playful learning has been mentioned, which can be viewed as a foundational concept closely linked to game-based learning (see e.g., Plass et al., 2015). In addition, the teaching of natural sciences emphasizes the importance of developing 21st-century skills, such as digital competencies (e.g., through digital technology-supported education).

Education for Sustainable Development

Within the *Finnish* curriculum, the theme of sustainability is especially relevant, crossing various subjects and underlying the curriculum itself as a foundational value. The root word for sustainability has up to 790 mentions within the entire curriculum. One practice that guides the development of the operational culture is “the responsibility over the environment and steering towards a sustainable future” (p.20). Additionally, the school's role in building a sustainable future has been mentioned in the first paragraph of the curriculum. The importance of sustainable development is also visible in the content level of specific subjects.

The themes of environmental awareness and ethical understanding are important aspects of the *Austrian* curriculum as well. The focus on sustainability and global citizenship complements Austria's commitment to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, ensuring that students are both educated and able to contribute to the future. Within the Austrian education system, sustainability has traditionally been promoted through various initiatives on the school level, such as the Austrian ECO-Schools Programme (ECOLOG, Rauch & Pfaffenwimmer, 2014).

Within the *Hungarian* curriculum, fostering ecological awareness and environmental consciousness are viewed as important aspects of attitude formation for students. Additionally, issues related to sustainability are promoted as part of the natural science subject, covering topics such as various ecosystems and their environmental issues, energy and basic atmospheric phenomena and processes. The topics can be approached through experience-oriented pedagogy and represent wicked problems.

Towards a Unified Understanding of Complex Educational Approaches in Curriculum Development

The curriculum comparison shows that national curricula can address contemporary educational approaches on various levels, ranging from general approaches to specific teaching and learning practices. Thus, different level characterizations can be used to foster meaningful, comprehensive and cohesive approaches towards education. For contemporary education, it is important to equip students with the ability to understand multidimensional phenomena that constitute today's world. However, this is not an easy task to achieve – for example, students tend to have a more binary view on right and wrong choices in regard to sustainable lifestyle while lacking a more in-depth understanding of complex sustainability topics (Kowasch & Lippe, 2019). Similarly, the seemingly straightforward process of bringing games to a classroom requires a flexible approach, with consideration towards the context, as well as the differences between countries in regards to curricula, pedagogy and practices (Allsop & Jessel, 2015). Thus, instead of focusing on the manifestation of a game as a digital product, it could be beneficial to refer to the educational approach that can engage learners on various levels (Plass et al., 2015).

When experiential education, game-based learning and education for sustainable development are discussed in parallel, it is possible to observe the similarities and differences between these constructs. Although sustainable development might be the most tangible part of the analysis due to its visibility in specific subjects and as a foundational value underlying education practices, it can also be reduced to the level of content knowledge. In the case of game-based learning, this can be contrasted with focusing on ICT use as such instead of the implications of specific pedagogical approaches enabled by ICT use. Experiential education, in turn, can be visible in the education practices used but could remain on a more superficial level (e.g., due to teachers' and students' understanding of the approach; Hofer et al., 2018). This suggests that there might be a need to go beyond these conceptualizations and focus on the core values and characteristics underlying the approaches. For example, efforts to design games should emphasize the process through which specific engagement occurs among learners and how this engagement, in particular, facilitates learning (Plass et al., 2015).

The educational approaches described in this study can be viewed as interlinked entities, calling for a similar level of attention on a curricular level. However, contemporary curricula are often created in an iterative way and follow earlier practices for curriculum planning, leading to fragmentation in how these concepts are introduced and discussed. Future efforts of curriculum planning should recognize experiential education, game-based learning and education for sustainable development as complex, foundational approaches to education and build a systematic path from general descriptions to consistent and meaningful teaching and learning practices. Additionally, teacher training and resource development must be emphasized to ensure integration between curriculum design and classroom practices.

Conclusions

This study contributes to research by describing the state of curricula in European countries in relation to complex educational approaches that are relevant to contemporary education. The results of the curriculum analysis

show that experiential education, game-based learning, and education for sustainable development can be considered at different levels of a national curriculum. The comparison of the curricula shows that European countries can take similar approaches to teaching complex topics. However, curricula tend to be layered entities that combine pragmatic teaching and learning strategies with more vague descriptions of educational approaches. This can make it difficult for teachers to identify and interpret the possibilities provided by the curriculum in a way that supports the intended ways of working. Towards practice, this study notes that it is important to maintain the flexibility of teaching and learning processes so that teachers and schools can tailor the contents to fit their students. However, the authorities responsible for curriculum planning should support this process by recognizing the dimensionality of contemporary educational approaches and how they can manifest and be consistently addressed on different levels of the curriculum.

In addition to educational researchers, the results of this study can be useful for teachers, school leaders and policy makers alike to inform decision-making and daily practice related to curricular activities. In a similar manner, game developers can use the information provided by the study to build understanding of the many layers that pertain to the use of games within the educational sphere. However, it is important to note that this study analyzed a limited number of national curricula in selected European countries, with the aim to compare and contrast the curricula on a descriptive level. Because of this, the observations made might not represent the phenomenon in other cultural and geographical contexts. Thus, more research is needed to characterize the different planes of contemporary education and how they are shaped through the use of innovative educational approaches.

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